

Participatory approach for conservation agriculture technology to increase maize production on dryland and semiarid for adaptation on climate change in NTB

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ABSTRACT

The reduction of the risk of agricultural failure due to climate change was implemented in the NTB province through conservation agriculture (CA) with three main pillars: minimum tillage or no tillage, continuously land cover crop and plant rotation or intercropping. Conservation agriculture in the long term may improve yields and simultaneously increase adaptation to climate change, especially in erratic rainfall conditions. The objective of this research was to apply conservation agriculture technology on dryland and semiarid climate type for maize cultivation through participatory approach. There were 46 farmer groups with a total of 953 members have involved to apply conservation agriculture through a field school approach. Each farmer group developed a CA plot as a joint learning tool compared to farmer practices. Farmer groups planted maize at all types of CA. This activity was conducted at 3 districts, 5 sub-districts and 9 villages in NTB province from 2014 to 2016. The average yield of maize crops with conservation agriculture during the four planting seasons from 2014 to 2016 was 3.9 ton/ha with an increase of 77% compared to the harvest of maize by the farmer practices (2.2 ton/ha). The average yield of maize in the rainy season of 2014 with CA techniques was 4.3 ton/ha; this yield was increase by 68% compared to farmer practice (2.6 ton/ha). In wet season of 2015, the average yield of maize with CA was 3.4 tons / ha and this was increased by 87% compared to farmers practices (1.8 tons / ha). Similar trend was also found in wet season of 2016 where yield of maize increased by 63% compared to farmers practices. Thus, Conservation agriculture consistently increased maize productivity and increased the income of farmers on uncertain climatic conditions.

Keywords: *Conservation agriculture, climate change, maize, field school, participatory*

INTRODUCTION

West Nusa Tenggara (NTB) with a land area covered for about 2.01 million hectares, has 84 percent or about 1.8 million hectares of dryland (BPS, 2016). NTB has the largest dryland area in Indonesia after NTT. The dryland of

NTB has not been used optimally to increase food production and so far the Government prioritized to develop wet land which may spur the inequality of farmer welfare in dryland.

Most of the land in West Nusa Tenggara Province, generally, is less fertile which has various limiting factors (physical, chemical and biological soil) that lead to low productivity (Ministry of Agriculture, 2009). Dryland required site-specific management and technology to increase production. Revitalization of policy and acceleration of dryland development may be a strategic option to improve the welfare of rural communities as most of the poor people in NTB live in the dryland and most of their livelihoods are dependent on agricultural activities on dryland. The existence of the agricultural development program in dryland would reach the poor community directly to improve their welfare.

Agriculture as a major source of livelihood in West Nusa Tenggara is very vulnerable to climate change. Climate change is the most stressful factor in decreasing productivity and production in the agricultural sector. Most dryland area has been planted once every year on wet season due to low and erratic rainfall. Food shortages especially in unfavorable seasons due to extreme climate change becomes challenges in NTB and its impact on smallholder households that have relatively limited land resources (subsistence). Furthermore, the influence of climate change has exacerbated by lack of sustainability land and crop management such as high erosion occurred, intensive tillage, land clearing by burning and excessive use of chemicals pesticide and fertilizers. This degradation of the land resource base has reduced crop yields and productivity factor, which forced farmers, scientists and development stakeholders to look for an alternative paradigm that is ecologically sustainable as well as profitable. Another challenge for agriculture is its environmental foot print and climate change. Agriculture is responsible for about 30% of the total greenhouse gas emissions of CO₂, N₂O and CH₄ while being directly affected by the consequences of a changing climate (IPCC, 2007).

Sustainable crop production intensification must not only reduce the impact of climate change on crop production but also mitigate the factors that cause climate change by reducing emissions and by contributing to carbon sequestration in soils. Intensification should also enhance biodiversity in crop production systems above and below the ground to improve ecosystem services for better productivity and healthier environment. A set of soil-crop-nutrient-water-landscape system management practices known as Conservation Agriculture (CA) has the potential to deliver on all of these goals (Hobbs, et al., 2012; Kassam et al., 2009; Friedrich et al., 2012).

According to FAO (2011), Conservation Agriculture (CA) is a farming system that promotes maintenance of a permanent soil cover, minimum soil disturbance (i.e. no tillage), and diversification of plant species. It enhances

biodiversity and natural biological processes above and below the ground surface, which contribute to increased water and nutrient use efficiency and to improved and sustained crop production. CA is characterized by three linked principles, namely: 1. Continuous no- or minimal mechanical soil disturbance (i.e., no-tillage and direct sowing or broadcasting of crop seeds, and direct placing of planting material in the soil; minimum soil disturbance from cultivation, harvest operation or farm traffic, in special cases limited strip tillage); 2. Permanent organic soil cover, especially by crop residues, crops and cover crops; and 3. Diversification of crop species grown in sequence or associations through rotations or, in case of perennial crops, associations of plants, including a balanced mix of legume and non legume crops (FAO, 2011; Friedrich et al., 2012).

Conservation Agriculture seeks to reduce risks due to extreme climate change through reducing soil tillage or zero tillage, permanent land cover, and crop rotation that may lead to increase population of soil organisms and organic carbon (Corsi et al., 2012), reducing the use of chemicals pesticides and fertilizers (Hobbs et al., 2012). Labor requirements are generally reduced by about 50%, which allows farmers to save time, fuel and machinery costs (Saturnino and Landers, 2002; Baker et al, 2007; Lindwall and Sonntag, 2011; Crabtree, 2010). Fuel savings in the order of around 65% are in general reported (Sorenson and Montoya, 1984; 1991). Through this approach it is expected that agricultural yields would increase the quality of land and water resources (Laurent et al., 2011). The introduction of the principles and practices of conservation agriculture to farmers and other stakeholders was carried out through some stages, including training at provincial, district, sub-district and farmers levels, practices and trials by farmers and field extensions. The implementation of Conservation Agriculture in West Nusa Tenggara means to increase maize production, improve soil structure and fertility. The objective of this research was to apply conservation agricultural technology on dryland and semiarid climate type for maize cultivation through participatory approach.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The conservation agriculture (CA) was conducted in 2014-2016 in 3 Districts (West Lombok, East Lombok, and Central Lombok Districts) and in 5 sub-districts (Pujut sub-district of Central Lombok, Gerung and Lembar sub-districts of West Lombok Districts and Jerowaru and Pringgabaya sub-districts of East Lombok District).

Conservation Agriculture was conducted by developing plots at the farmer group level. The participatory learning process at the group level was conducted through the Conservation Agriculture Field School (CAFS) where each farmer group developed demonstration plots of CA with an area varying

between 0.05 and 0.13 ha. Land preparation with the CA approach was carried out in a participatory manner involving group members and local agricultural extension officers. There were two CA methods involved (planting hole and ripping) and farmer practices. The hole was made at dimension of 40 cm x 40 x 40cm and filled with 5 kg compost manures thoroughly mix with soil; planted with maize at each corner of the hole. Ripping was made through ripping soil at 10 depth and filled compost manures. The CA methods were compare with farmer practices. Maize cultivation technology in the field was referred to integrated crop management (PTT) (Agricultural Research and Development, 2010). The processes of the planning, establishment, implementation, and maintenance of the CA plots were conducted through participatory learning by means of farmer field schools (FFSs) approach. Each farmer group has conducted their trial for FFS.

Each group of farmers held regular meeting for 9 times (2 times a week) in one planting season to observe, study and record changes that occurred in the CAFS sites. Agronomic observations were carried out in a participatory manner with farmers include observing vegetative and generative growth, and harvesting of maize plants. Data from observations were analyzed using descriptive and statistical methods. Survey was conducted to obtain to what extent of farmers understanding and their perception on CA practice. There were 100 participants of farmers cooperator and 11 non participants (non co-operator) were sampled.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Land Characteristic

The selection of the three locations was based on 3 different agro-ecosystems where the CA location in West Lombok District represents the agroforestry agro-ecosystem. Maize was planted on undulating to hilly land with a slope of 10-25%. The main crops on the land are wood trees planted on the smooth and bench terraces while maize was planted on the terraced land. Site of CA in Central Lombok district represents rainfed agro-ecosystem with a cropping index of 100 to 200 per year. In rainy season (wet season) the land was planted with rice with a no-tillage system (TOT). Land in second planting season (dry season) was planted with maize as soil moisture highly available. Site of CA in East Lombok district represents dryland and semi-arid agro-ecosystem. Planting maize was conducted once year in rainy season starting from December to March.

Monthly rainfall distribution for 13, 65 and 8 years for the Lembar, Pujut and Pringabaya sub-district respectively are shown in Figure 1. The amount of rainfall in average year for the three locations is 1429 mm, 1626 mm and 754 mm

for Lembar, Pujut and Pringgabaya, respectively. The lowest rainfall occurred in Pringgabaya and the highest in Pujut sub-district. Results of analysis on rainfall data indicated that farmers may be suitable to start planting crop on November, December and January for Pujut, Lembar and Pringgabaya sub-district, respectively.

Figure 1. Distribution of average monthly rainfall for Lembar (13 years), Pujut (65 years) and Pringgabaya (8 years).

Participatory CA trial

Land size distribution for CA trials in each district is shown in Table 1. Land site for farmer practices as control trials (non CA) was adjusted to CA plot trial. The number of farmers involved in CA trial was 944 person and total land size engaged for both CA was 6.54 ha. Land characteristic and member farmers involved in each location was vary due to the willingness of farmers to participate in conservation agriculture trial. The number of farmer groups involved in FFS was 43 and total farmers was 944.

Productivity of maize at CA and non CA treatments for FFS during three consecutive years of wet season (WS) 2014/2015, WS 2015/2016 and WS 2016/2017 is shown in Figure 2. In general, CA practices influenced productivity of maize in all years and all locations compared to farmer practices. Maize productivity was higher at CA treatment than that non CA treatment. In wet season of 2014/2015, productivity of maize at CA treatment increased by 53% compared to farmer practice.

In wet season of 2015/2016, yield of maize decreased for both treatment of CA and non CA compared to wet season of 2014/2015 and 2016/2017. This was due to elnino year occurred in 2016 that influence the yield of maize (data not presented). However, yield of maize in CA treatment was significantly higher than that of non CA treatment in an elnino year. This indicated that

maize cultivation could be more tolerant to drought due to limited rainfall (elnino) in CA practices compared to farmers practices.

Table 1. Distribution of land for CA and non CA trial for FFS at three district in NTB.

District	Sub-District	Villages	Farmer groups	Farmers group members	Plot size (ha)	
					CA	Non CA
Lombok Barat	Lembar	Mareje Timur	11	184	0.77	0.77
		Jembatan Gantung	2	36	0.07	0.07
	Gerung	Giri Tembesi	1	20	0.04	0.04
SubTotal	2	3	14	242	0.9	0.9
Lombok Tengah	Pujut	Sukadana	9	181	0.78	0.78
SubTotal	1	2	12	277	1.7	1.7
Lombok Timur	Pringgabaya	Gunung Malang	5	76	0.50	0.50
		Sekaroh	7	207	0.33	0.33
	Jerowaru	Pemongkong	3	86	0.24	0.24
SubTotal	2	4	17	425	1.2	1.2
Total	5	9	43	944	3.27	3.27

In wet season 2016/2017, yield of maize was consistently and significantly higher in CA practices than in non CA practices. The highest yield of maize during three year trial occurred during the wet season 2016/2017 for both CA and non CA practices. This was due to the favorable environment of maize to grow in higher rainfall (data not presented).

Figure 2. Productivity of maize at CA and non CA treatments for three consecutive years trial in wet season (WS) 2014/2015, WS 2015/2016 and WS 2016/2017.

Adoption and scale up of CA practiced by farmers

Adoption and scale up of CA practiced by co-operator farmers and non co-operator in three districts during three implementation of CA is shown in Table 2. In general, farmers were very enthusiasm in adopting the CA practices. The result of survey has also underlined farmer’s participation and proactive action to adopt appropriate conservation agriculture technology and practices by resource-poor smallholder farmers through community-based participatory extension approaches has led them to better agriculture practices.

Table 2. Adoption and scale up of CA practiced by farmers in three district locations.

Districts	Sub-district	Farmers number	CA cooperator		CA non cooperator		Total adopters	Total land (Ha)
			Farmers number	size (Ha)	Farmers number	size (ha)		
Lombok Barat	Lembar	237	80	13	20	2	100	15
	Gerung	20	6	0.75	6	0.9	12	1.65
Lombok Tengah	Pujut	277	171	23.55	50	11.54	221	35.09
Lombok Timur	Pringgabaya	59	40	22.3	20	0.9	60	23.2
	Jerowaru	363	218	50.02	80	16.94	298	66.96
Total	5	956	515	109.62	176	32.28	691	141.9

CONCLUSIONS

Conservation agriculture consistently increased maize productivity and increased the income of farmers on uncertain climatic conditions. Maize cultivation was more tolerant to drought condition due to elnino in CA practices compared to farmer practices. Farmers were very enthusiasm in adopting the CA practices. Farmers have high participation and proactive action to adopt appropriate conservation agriculture technology and practices by resource-poor smallholder farmers through community-based participatory extension approaches which has led them to better agriculture practices.

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